

Received / Makale Geliş Tarihi 11.09.2023
Published / Yayınlanma Tarihi 30.11.2023
Volume / Issue (Cilt/Sayı)-ss/pp 10(101), 2951-2961

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.10253445

Lecturer Serdar Kızılcan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8209-2804>

Uşak University, Civil Aviation Vocational School, Uşak / TURKEY

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/05es91y67>

Airline Cabin Crew Employees and Quiet Quitting: An Evaluation from the Perspective of Cabin Chiefs

Havayolu Kabin Ekibi Çalışanları ve Sessiz İstifa: Kabin Amirleri Açısından Bir Değerlendirme

ABSTRACT

Quiet quitting is a negative organizational behavior that occurs in businesses. It is well known that employee behaviors have a direct impact on the productivity and profitability of businesses. Therefore, eliminating the occurrence of quiet quitting in businesses will motivate and satisfy employees, thus ensuring that the service quality of businesses is maintained at a high level. In this study, findings obtained from cabin supervisors working in an airline company in Antalya using the semi-structured interview technique, one of the qualitative research methods, are discussed. According to the results of the study quiet quitting can arise among employees for various reasons. Accordingly, quiet quitting can occur due to reasons such as the absence of regular working hours, not being able to allocate enough time to personal life, long duty shifts, lack of recognition for achievements, failure of aspiring cabin supervisors to become supervisors, low wages, strict enforcement of company rules, and not letting mistakes go unpunished. Some employees who engage in quiet quitting tend to avoid taking on responsibilities during flights. It is observed that some of them have low motivation and obtain medical certificates to avoid flying.

Keywords: Quiet Quitting, Civil Aviation, Cabin Attendant, Airline Company.

ÖZET

Personel davranışlarının işletmelerin üretkenliği ve karlılığı üzerinde doğrudan etkisi olduğu bilinmektedir. Bu nedenle, işletmelerde ortaya çıkabilecek sessiz istifayı ortadan kaldırmak, çalışanların motive ve memnun olmalarını sağlayacak ve böylece işletmelerin hizmet kalitesi de artacaktır. Bu çalışmada kalitatif çalışma yöntemlerinden biri olan yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme tekniği kullanılarak Antalya'da faaliyet gösteren bir havayolu şirketinde çalışan kabin amirlerinden elde edilen bulgular tartışılmıştır. Çalışmanın sonuçlarına göre sessiz istifa'nın çalışanlarda farklı nedenlerden dolayı ortaya çıktığı görülmektedir. Buna göre sessiz istifa rutin çalışma saatlerinin olmayışı, özel hayata yeterince vakit ayıramama, uzun yatı görevleri, başarıların takdir edilmemesi, kabin amiri adaylarının amir olamayışı, düşük maaş, şirkette katı kuralların uygulanması gibi nedenlerden dolayı ortaya çıkabilir. Bazı sessiz istifa eden çalışanlar uçuşlarda sorumluluk almaktan kaçınmaktadır. Bazılarının düşük motivasyona sahip oldukları, uçuşa gitmemek için sağlık raporu aldıkları görülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sessiz İstifa, Sivil Havacılık, Kabin Ekibi, Havayolu Şirketi.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of the aviation industry from the past to the present, the increasingly competitive conditions have forced airline companies to provide higher quality services and meet the expectations of their customers. One of the key conditions for providing quality service and meeting expectations is the presence of employees who enjoy their work, take responsibility, and work with high efficiency. When we anticipate that cabin crew members in the quiet quitting process adopt a monotonous working method and make minimal effort, it is certain that these individuals will not meet the company's expectations.

Being a member of the cabin crew requires interacting with passengers on every flight assignment and performing numerous tasks at a high pace. Managers who do not know or do not care about how to motivate and retain employees who do not complement each other and are not dedicated can lead employees to enter the quiet quitting process. Therefore, this research can be a valuable resource for professionals and employers in the aviation industry, helping them better understand the needs of airline cabin crew members and improve their work. Additionally, it can provide recommendations on how to prevent quiet quittings and strategies for employers to retain their employees.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAME

2.1. The Concept of Quiet Quitting

According to Pearce (2022), the concept of quiet quitting was first used by Bryan Creely, a corporate recruiter and career coach based in Nashville, in a video published on TikTok and YouTube on March 4, 2022, as mentioned in his article in the Los Angeles Times. The concept of quiet quitting does not refer to an employee actually leaving their job but rather to the employee doing "neither more nor less" than what is required for the compensation they receive. In a general sense, this concept implies that employees exhibit retirement-like behavior when they are employed and only do the minimum required for their jobs. In short, this concept can be defined as the realization that putting in extra effort for one's job will not yield any rewards, leading the individual to continue their work with the least possible effort (Seçer, 2011). When an employee begins working for a company, an unwritten internal contract (psychological contract) forms between the employee and the organization. If this contract is violated by the organization, the employee can choose to remain silent or attempt to restore balance by speaking out. If the balance cannot be restored, the employee may decide to leave the job. Employees who do not leave their jobs may opt for a quiet quitting by terminating the psychological contract instead of the formal employment contract (Scheibner and Hapkemeyer, 2013).

Quiet quitting should not be confused with laziness. Quiet quitting focuses on a situation where a person, while being satisfied with their current job, lacks the motivation to do more. This individual does not actively seek development opportunities, does not improve their skills, and does not explore new ways of working. They only perform enough to stay in their current position and are content with remaining there. When looking at the definition of quiet quitting it does not appear that unhappiness is the leading factor; it can be said that the issue is related to employee motivation. Employees who quiet quitting do not go beyond their duties, do not use their creativity, and do not care about workplace expectations. Individuals who embrace the feeling of quiet quitting in the work environment can negatively affect the organizational commitment levels of other employees and may lead to a loss of productivity. Although this concept is relatively new in the literature, it has been met with significant academic and professional interest. Therefore, it can be said that the foundations on which the newly researched concept of quiet quitting is based have not yet been definitively established (Kumar, 2022).

2.2. The Reasons for Quiet Quitting

One of the most important reasons why employees resort to quiet quitting is their desire to improve or protect their mental health. Additionally, there is a desire to prevent burnout, alleviate stress, or cope with stress, as well as an aspiration to achieve a better work-life balance. Employees tend to have a negative view of demands coming from the workplace because they believe they will not be adequately rewarded for working more (Hitchins, 2022). When organizations fail to communicate their goals and strategies effectively to employees and do not invest in their professional development, employees feel uncertain about the future. Quiet quitting can be a reasonable response, especially for employees who do not perceive the organization as transparent in its communication with them. On the other hand, being a member of an organization is not sufficient for a sense of belonging. When employees feel excluded from decisions related to their work, they feel disconnected from their colleagues and the company, and they do not fully feel like they belong (Schroth, 2019).

When considering the two most prominent generations affected by quiet quitting can be a reasonable response, especially for employees who do not perceive the organization as transparent in its communication with them. Generation Y and Generation Z, it can be said that one of the most significant reasons for quiet quitting is the work-life imbalance brought about by COVID-19. Many researchers point out that work-life imbalance is one of the primary reasons for quiet quitting (Hymes, 2021). Quiet quitting can occur for different reasons for each individual. Lack of motivation, lack of flexibility, unfair treatment, monotony, wage disparities, inequality, and inability to work in a team environment are some of the situations that can lead to the adoption of quiet quitting (Tong, 2022).

2.3. Signs of Quiet Quitting

There are several indicators of quiet quitting behavior. According to Echterhoff et al. (1997), the signs of quiet quitting behavior can be listed as follows:

- Being indifferent to occurring conflicts.
- Responding to questions with brief yes or no answers.

- Avoiding tasks assigned to them.
- Not resisting interference with their authority.
- Implementing decisions of superiors without questioning their correctness.
- Lack of passion or enthusiasm.
- Not offering any suggestions or criticism in response to problems.
- Aligning with the majority even when they believe it's wrong on certain matters.
- Not aspiring for career advancement.
- Behaving casually in work relationships.
- Coming late to work or leaving early.
- Avoiding taking on special assignments.
- Not participating in company events organized for social purposes.
- Not neglecting family and personal life due to work-related issues.

2.4. Stages of Quiet Quitting

Quiet quitting consists of three stages: Emotional stage, mental stage, and physiological stage. Initially, in the Emotional stage, the employee is not entirely sure about what they are experiencing and cannot make a definite decision about what they will do in the future. Internally, they experience a conflict between the desire to stay and the decision to leave. The second stage, known as the Mental stage, is called chronic disengagement. In this stage, the employee evaluates how well they are supported in the workplace. Even though the employee continues to actively contribute to their job, they are no longer emotionally attached to the intense work culture (such as tight deadlines and long working hours). In this stage, deliberately avoiding high levels of stress is common. The employee is affected by the realization that they are not emotionally connected to the employer. In the Physiological stage, the employee openly expresses their discomfort and requests for time off. They do not hide the fact that they are actively considering new job opportunities related to their work (Gupte, 2022).

2.5. Quiet Quitting Consequences

At first glance, quiet quitting may not appear to be a problem. Those who engage in quiet quitting choose not to leave their core duties and responsibilities. However, for many businesses, a workforce willing to go beyond the call of duty represents a critical competitive advantage. The reality is that because most jobs are not precisely defined in formal job descriptions or contracts, businesses rely on their employees to meet extra demands. Therefore, it is not surprising that many leaders react negatively to the trend of quiet quitting. In fact, many leaders argue that it is difficult to lose employees who want to leave, but it is even worse for these employees not to resign because it increases the workload (Ratnatunga, 2022).

Employees who engage in quiet quitting and continue to work with low performance before eventually leaving will cause significant long-term harm to the organization. Explicit resignations have a clear and immediate negative impact on productivity and costs in existing roles. However, quiet quitting, with its long-term negative impact on organizational efficiency, can be a highly dangerous situation (Yıldız, 2023). Increased absenteeism due to quiet quitting will disrupt workflow in businesses, make teamwork more difficult, and ultimately reduce the capacity to produce products or services. Additionally, it's important to note that replacing absent employees with new hires and training them will create additional costs for businesses (Robinson, 2022).

One of the other risks in businesses where quiet quitting is observed is low job quality. However, it would be wrong to think of job quality here only in terms of the quality of the products and services produced. Because job quality is directly related to the accuracy, speed, efficiency, and customer satisfaction of the work performed. Therefore, even a slight decrease in job quality can negatively affect the reputation and income of the business (Srivastava and Kanpur, 2014). Along with the low job quality triggered by quiet quitting, a decrease in customer satisfaction is inevitable. Due to the low job quality, brand value and loyalty will decrease. This will lead to dissatisfied customers making negative comments about the business or product/service (Xu, 2020).

2.6. Studies on Quiet Quitting

For over 20 years, Gallup, an organization in the United States that focuses on workforce productivity, has been conducting research on workplace-related issues. They have expressed that the results are far from encouraging, with employee engagement dropping as low as 32%. According to the findings of a study conducted in June 2022 with over 15,000 participants, "quiet quitters" make up at least 50% of the U.S. workforce. Factors such as supply chain issues and employment dynamics due to the pandemic are said to be triggering the number of quiet quitting (Gallup, 2022). In a study conducted online in Türkiye in September 2022 by the Youthall Career Platform, it was found that 24% of young people are in the process of quiet quitting, 46.7% are inclined towards this concept, 15% are "not inclined towards this approach," and 14.4% responded with "I don't know what it is" (Youthall, 2022). According to a report by Axios/Generation Lab, another research company, a significant number of employees in the 18-29 age group, partially referred to as Generation Z, are undergoing quiet quitting. 82% of the young people surveyed mentioned that they want to work with minimum effort and that focusing on career goals is not a top priority in life. When looking at their priorities, spending time with family and friends, taking care of their health, and pursuing hobbies were reported to be of greater importance (Pandey, 2022).

Arar et al. (2023) based their study on scientific theories that could explain the concept of quiet quitting within a cause-and-effect relationship. In this context, they concluded that the Conservation of Resources Theory, Social Exchange Theory, and Theory of Generations are the most comprehensive theories that can explain this concept. They then examined the possible antecedents and expected outcomes of this concept. Hiltunen (2023) conducted research on employees in the Finnish aviation industry. According to the results of the study, two key factors of quiet quitting are a lack of respect for the employee and a lack of trust in the employer. Furthermore, it was noted that quiet quitting primarily concerns younger generations. Most Generation Y (Millennial) employees are considering changing jobs within the past year. The study suggested that motivation factors such as better management, more flexibility, and higher pay could be components that prevent people from reaching the threshold of quiet quitting.

2.7. Cabin Crew Concept

In aircraft engaged in passenger transportation, the individuals responsible for implementing necessary safety and security measures and ensuring passenger comfort are defined as "cabin crew" or "flight attendants" (SHGM, 2023). According to another definition, a cabin crew member is a qualified individual who, in accordance with the operational instructions of their affiliated airline company that complies with quality and flight safety standards, fulfills national and international civil aviation requirements and flight safety measures to ensure passenger safety, security, and comfort (Aktunç, 2013). Cabin crew members are required to be active and vigilant when preparing the aircraft on the ground, welcoming passengers, throughout every stage of the flight, and when bidding farewell to passengers. They play a critical role in terms of passenger comfort, and the behavior of cabin crew members towards passengers directly impacts the service quality and customer satisfaction of the airline company. Depending on their experience and qualifications, individuals working as cabin crew can become cabin chiefs, check pursers, and instructors, provided they meet national and international aviation requirements.

2.8. Cabin Crew's Personal Attitudes and Behaviors

The attitudes and behaviors that cabin crew members should exhibit are listed as follows:

- Being polite and smiling towards crew members and passengers.
- Creating the impression that serving passengers is a pleasure.
- Meeting the passenger's requests to the extent possible with the available resources.
- Not providing misleading information about the company and colleagues.
- Being harmonious with colleagues.
- Representing the company in the best possible way.
- Adhering to company procedures and standards during the duty.
- Avoiding behaviors that could damage the company's prestige.
- Following uniform rules.

- Showing empathy.
- Remaining composed in stressful situations.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Purpose and Importance of Research

In the increasingly competitive conditions of the airline industry, the importance of customer satisfaction for airline companies is growing. Cabin crew members, who are the face of airline companies and interact directly with passengers, are therefore a vital component of the aviation system. The aim of this study is to evaluate the phenomenon of quiet quitting behavior among cabin crew members, who provide face-to-face services and work in a labor-intensive manner, and to understand the reasons behind it. As quiet quitting is a relatively new concept, a review of the literature reveals that there have been no prior studies conducted on the quiet quitting of cabin crew members. It is expected that this research will make a significant contribution in this regard.

3.2. Population and Sample of the Research

The population of the research consists of cabin crew members working for an airline company operating in Antalya province. The sample of the study consists of cabin chiefs employed by this company. In airline companies, cabin crews go on their flights according to their personal flight schedules. A different cabin crew is assigned for each flight. Therefore, the ability of cabin chiefs to interact with different employees and their experience in forming opinions and evaluations about employees have a direct impact on this study. A total of 15 cabin chiefs were reached for the study. However, 3 cabin chiefs declined to provide any input, citing concerns about potential issues with the company, and 2 cabin chiefs stated that they had not experienced any incidents related to the research topic.

3.3. Data Collection and Research Methodology

Granger (2022) has expressed doubts about how quiet quitting can truly be measured or detected, stating, "The fact that it is silent certainly makes it difficult to measure." In this context, this study was conducted through qualitative research. Qualitative research, especially when combined with purposive sampling, allows for in-depth and extensive information to be obtained from a small number of participants (Curtisa et al., 2000). In this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 cabin chiefs between August 7th and 22nd, 2023, using the purposive sampling selection method. Semi-structured interviews involve predetermined questions but also allow for the addition of different questions during the interview to obtain more in-depth information as the situation requires (Tümüklü, 2000).

During the interviews with cabin chiefs, they were informed about the research topic, and a brief presentation on "quiet quitting" was provided to them. The interviews were scheduled based on the cabin chiefs' days off, taking into consideration their flight schedules. Some of the interviews were conducted online or through video conferencing applications. Notes were taken during the interviews, and a voice recording device was used. Each participant was assigned a code to ensure that the research did not create any reservations among the cabin chiefs.

3.4. Limitations of the Research

This study was conducted only among cabin chiefs employed by a single airline company due to the difficulty in reaching employees of all airline companies. Some cabin chiefs could not be reached due to their layover duty. The research findings may vary based on the positive or negative experiences cabin chiefs may have after participating in the study.

3.5. Findings

Out of the cabin chiefs who participated in the research, 7 were female, and 4 were male. The age range of the research group falls between 29 and 44 years old. The total duration of their experience as cabin chiefs varies from 3 to 13 years. The cabin chiefs' overall experience as cabin crew members ranges from 7 to 19 years. The majority of the group has between 10 to 14 years of total experience. Participant confidentiality was maintained by assigning codes from CC1 to CC10 (CC: Cabin Chief).

In the interviews with cabin chiefs, when asked, "Can you notice a cabin crew member who quiet quitting during the pre-flight briefings (meetings) conducted as a team?" CC3 responded as follows: "Our communication with the cabin crew begins with the pre-flight briefing. Besides friends we have worked with before or know, there are also colleagues who we are flying with for the first time. Some of these

colleagues may give the impression during the briefing that they are physically present but mentally elsewhere. I think maybe they have personal problems or they might be tired due to the intensity of the flights. However, their behavior remains the same on subsequent flights, and our conversations reveal the situation. These colleagues seem to have the mindset of 'I do my job, and I don't get involved in the rest.'"

CC6 answered the same question as follows: "Colleagues who often exhibit quiet quitting behavior are noticeable during the briefing. For example, some colleagues have only been on the job for 3 months, but they show no enthusiasm or interest. These colleagues cannot find what they expect from the profession due to the conditions and challenges of the job, so they continue working until their contracts expire. Some of them just do their assigned tasks, and there's no problem with that, but others act as if they're not even on the plane and reduce the effectiveness of the team."

Regarding the question, "What are the reasons for quiet quitting among cabin crew members?" CC4 responded as follows: "Our job doesn't have a concept of regular working hours. Weekends or public holidays don't mean much to us because we have to adhere to our flight schedule. Especially some new colleagues can't adapt to the irregular work life and are forced to work until their contracts end. Naturally, we can't get satisfactory performance from some of these colleagues, unfortunately."

CC8 expresses a similar rationale as follows: "Just like in any job, our profession has its own set of challenges. One of them is the lack of regular working hours. While people sleep at night, we are flying or spending days or weeks away from home during layovers. We have to adjust our personal lives to our work. Some colleagues can't cope with this situation. Especially some married colleagues can't fully commit to their work because they can't spend time with their families or children. They do what's required, but they are not mentally fully engaged."

An employee who feels that their sacrifices are overlooked shared their views with CC2 as follows: "I don't think the company values its employees enough or appreciates their achievements. When I feel valued or appreciated, I go the extra mile for the company. Otherwise, I just do my job without going the extra mile. Recently, they called me on my day off and said that an aircraft had a malfunction, the cabin crew on the plane had exceeded their duty hours, they had to form a new crew, and they were in a tight spot, so they had to call me. I agreed to go on the flight. The passengers had been waiting at the airport for hours, and as soon as we boarded the plane, they became very aggressive, and they had harsh words for us. Despite everything, we managed the flight smoothly. But the next day, they called me again during my rest hours and said that I had delivered insufficient money from the in-flight sales service and asked for an account of the missing money. I agreed to go on a flight on my day off, dealt with difficult passengers, and instead of thanking me, they questioned the money. Because of incidents like this and similar ones, I only do what is asked of me. No one should expect sacrifice from me anymore."

According to CC7's observation, one of the main reasons for quiet quitting is the lack of career opportunities within the company. CC7 continues his statement as follows: "We have friends in the company who, even though the time for promotion to cabin chief has come, still haven't become chiefs. Some of these friends have the necessary experience and meet the criteria for promotion, but unfortunately, they are not maintaining their past performance, and they have lost hope."

CC1 expresses another reason as follows: "Occasionally, new friends join our team. The average age of these friends is low, around 20-23 years old. Some of them have received aviation training at university. During interviews, we ask candidates if they understand that our job is challenging and whether they can handle it. Some friends think that they can do this job no matter what, just to get into the company, and they say they can handle it. But unfortunately, things don't always go as they hoped. Our job requires responsibility; the safety, comfort, and satisfaction of passengers are important. We know what to do in emergencies and act accordingly. However, some friends mistakenly believe that this job is only about traveling and seeing new places. When they realize it's not like that, it's often too late."

CC10 suggests that some employees believe their salaries are not sufficient. They compare their salaries to those of their friends working in other companies and feel that they deserve higher pay. However, they express their dissatisfaction only during flights and are hesitant to voice their requests and demands to upper management. Some of their friends who can switch to other companies resign, while those who cannot continue to work.

CC9 expresses a similar reason as follows: "People think our salaries are very high. In reality, cabin crew members at other airlines do not receive as high salaries as those at Turkish Airlines. There have been times when we were put on unpaid leave when there were fewer flights. Low pay, late payment of salaries

and per diems inevitably affect me negatively. Is the company giving me the salary I deserve or paying it on time when it expects dedication and commitment from me? I just do my job; I don't get involved in the rest."

CC5 states that strict rules are enforced within the company, and mistakes are not forgiven. They express the situation as follows: "We are human, and of course, we can make mistakes. Even in mistakes made during flights that have no relation to the supervisor, supervisors can be punished. They receive warnings or lose their supervisor title. In my opinion, this is not the right approach. For example, a colleague working in the back of the plane accidentally inflates the slide, and the cabin supervisor in charge at the front loses their position. I understand giving a warning to the colleague who inflated the slide, and I can understand reducing their seniority, but why is the supervisor who is not at fault losing their position? Because of such examples, unfortunately, these colleagues lose their sense of belonging and break their emotional ties with the company."

CC3, a similar reason as follows: "Our company doesn't let any mistake go unpunished. Even the slightest error results in employees losing their cabin chief titles, having their seniority reduced, or receiving warnings. We had a very experienced and professional check purser who many believed would become a trainer. However, due to a mistake made during one flight, they also lost their check purser title. The mistake was as follows: When the aircraft is on the ground, it needs to take in water into the clean water tank on board. The hot water used for tea and coffee and the water from the lavatories are supplied from this tank. Check purser checks whether water has been taken into the aircraft from the front panel. After passengers had boarded, the aircraft's doors were closed, and it had left the parking position and was moving towards the runway. At that moment, the check purser realized they had not checked the water from the front panel and saw that the water tank was empty. They immediately informed the captain, and the captain returned to the parking position. After taking in water, they continued the flight. Check purser had to report this to the company, so the company requested a defense, and after the evaluation, check purser title was taken away from him. Our friend sent an email to the cabin services manager, expressing their love for the job and stating that the decision was too harsh, but they received no response. This situation inevitably had a negative impact on their flights, and his enthusiasm waned. After working for a while longer, he resigned. He is currently working as a trainer in another company."

CC6's response to the question "How does quiet quitting affect flights?" is as follows: "While there are some who do their job well, those who quiet quitting tend to have low motivation. Some avoid communication as much as possible, while others display indifference while performing their duties. During flights, I sometimes notice that the workload of other cabin crew members increases."

CC1 stated that employees who exhibit quiet quitting behavior generally show reluctance to resolve passenger problems and avoid taking responsibility. "Our job is not just about preparing for the flight and serving. We also need to fulfill the passenger's requests if possible or provide alternatives. For example, if there is an empty seat on the plane, a colleague can seat a tall passenger in a suitable seat and inform me, but they don't want to make the effort."

CC8 mentioned that some of these employees occasionally take sick leave and do not go on flights: "When someone takes sick leave and doesn't go on the flight, another cabin crew member goes in their place. It's also a matter of conscience. I wouldn't feel comfortable taking sick leave and having someone else go on the flight in my place when I'm not actually sick."

CC4's statement is as follows: "I believe that the energy of everyone in the cabin crew affects each other. When the cabin chief is lively, positive, and motivating, the cabin crew works accordingly. If the cabin chief's mood is low or their communication is weak, the team also behaves accordingly. The same applies to us. When everyone in the team is focused on their work, energetic, and cheerful, we absorb that energy, and the flight goes very well. But when I fly with a team that just wants the flight to end so they can go home, I also start thinking the same thing."

CC10 mentioned that some employees who quiet quitting speak negatively about the company during flights: "Those who stay silent in company meetings express their concerns during flights. They work on one hand and complain on the other. They talk about low salaries, delayed flight bonuses, unequal treatment of employees, and so on. There's a constant sense of dissatisfaction. I don't want to be on the same team with these colleagues because they create a negative atmosphere during flights."

CC5 approaches this question from a different perspective: "Occasionally, cabin crew members who quiet quitting resist instructions and try to appear indifferent. I even witness them trying to assert themselves on

certain issues. There's no point in questioning procedures and instructions. Sometimes, flight times are very short, and we struggle to complete our tasks. Dealing with such a colleague in this intense environment naturally creates tension."

In response to the question, "Why aren't these employees resigning?" CC3 answered as follows: "As cabin chiefs, when we notice that someone in the team has low motivation or issues, we prefer to talk to them. I asked a colleague who said they didn't enjoy their job during a flight why they didn't quit. He mentioned feeling like he was working in vain but didn't want to quit because as he gets older, he doesn't have the energy required to start a new job."

CC9 expressed their opinion as follows: "Most of those who are not satisfied with the working conditions or salary policy apply to other airline companies. Some of them do not meet the criteria of the company they apply to or fail their exams. Some cannot apply for jobs because there is a gentleman's agreement among companies. In other words, employees working in our company cannot apply to a company with which there is a gentleman's agreement, and similarly, employees of a company with a gentleman's agreement cannot apply to our company. Especially during the busy season, companies that do not want to lose their employees to each other make this agreement among themselves. Due to reasons like this, the concerned individuals cannot switch to another company and are forced to continue working here."

According to CC7, some of the employees in the quiet quitting process who cannot become cabin chief are not willing to give up the experience and seniority they have gained at the company to start as juniors in another company. "For example, at Turkish Airlines, the experience of experienced candidates is not taken into account. In interviews, they are asked if they can work under the responsibility of younger or less experienced employees. Those who accept the job and get hired may encounter problems such as team conflicts during flights."

According to CC2, employees in the quiet quitting process who want to switch to another sector cannot meet the experience and age criteria. "These friends who want to change jobs are not hired because they do not have previous experience. Some of them have worked in this sector for years, so their ages have advanced. These people need to sustain their lives, and among them, there are married individuals with children. They have to continue working until they find an alternative."

CC2's response to the question "What are the consequences of quiet quitting?" is as follows: "As a cabin crew, failing to perform our job properly can have negative effects on the passenger experience. Passengers are now more aware, they know what to expect, they research, share their experiences on social media, and can be sensitive. For example, if a passenger is not welcomed when they board the plane, they can complain about the crew or even send an email to the company stating that the crew didn't smile during the flight. In this context, the lack of services necessary for passenger comfort can lead to passenger dissatisfaction and damage the airline company's reputation."

According to CC3, quiet quitting can lead to the loss of senior and well-performing cabin crew employees for the airline company: "Experience is crucial in aviation. Airline companies should be aware of this and take steps to prevent quiet quittings among employees."

The statement from CC6 is as follows: "Due to quiet quitting, some colleagues leave their jobs or are let go. The company then hires new employees to replace them. The training and integration of new personnel into the company can be both time-consuming and costly for the company."

CC1 has expressed that the tendency of quiet quitting among cabin crew weakens teamwork: "When crew members quiet quitting, their commitment and motivation to their jobs often decrease. This affects team cohesion negatively. Without team cohesion, we cannot work in a coordinated manner, and responding quickly to an emergency situation may become more difficult."

CC10 has supported this view by stating: "Cabin crew members experiencing a lack of collaboration and harmony due to quiet quitting can have a negative impact on flight operations. Intra-team communication and coordination may become more challenging, which can hinder flights from being carried out on time and smoothly."

CC4 has noted that quiet quitting negatively impacts employees' careers, stating: "Airlines typically expect employees to take initiative, demonstrate leadership within their teams, and go above and beyond in their roles. Those who quiet quitting may fail to meet these expectations, making career progression difficult. While those who start their jobs at the same time or later may receive promotions and become cabin chiefs,

those who quiet quitting may miss out on promotion or advancement opportunities because they have not met the criteria for leadership."

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The aviation sector has been one of the rapidly growing industries throughout history. The rapid growth of the sector, along with increased competitive conditions, has led airline companies to strive for competitive advantage by providing better services than their competitors. In this context, cabin crew members, who serve as the face of airline companies and directly communicate and provide services to passengers, play a pivotal role. Therefore, the performance of cabin crew members directly affects the service quality of airline companies.

Hence, this study focused on the concept of quiet quitting in aviation and discussed the findings obtained from cabin chiefs (supervisors) working at an airline company in Antalya using a semi-structured interview technique. The interviews revealed that quiet quitting can occur for various reasons, both in theory and practice, for each individual. Factors such as irregular working hours, insufficient time for personal life, and long-haul flights have driven some cabin crew members towards quiet quitting. Other factors leading to quiet quitting include the company's failure to value employees adequately, a lack of recognition for achievements, and the inability of cabin crew members to become supervisors. On the other hand, quiet quitting can also be caused by low salaries, delayed payment of salaries and layover allowances, strict company policies, and repercussions for mistakes made within the company.

Quiet quitting manifests itself differently in flight operations. Some employees who quiet quitting tend to avoid taking responsibility during flights. Additionally, some exhibit low motivation, obtain medical certificates to avoid flights, and display a careless attitude. On the other hand, quiet quitting has negative consequences for both employees and the company. It can weaken teamwork and cooperation among cabin crew members, which can adversely affect flight operations. Those who quiet quitting may fail to meet the criteria for leadership and thus miss out on promotion or advancement opportunities. Quiet quitting can also lead to airlines losing experienced and competent cabin crew members. Hiring and integrating new employees to replace those who leave due to quiet quitting can be a time and cost burden for companies.

How should cabin chiefs manage quiet quitting from their perspective?

Cabin chiefs should ensure open and effective communication among the cabin crew, manage the workload of employees effectively, and monitor their progress. Understanding employee dissatisfaction, listening to their concerns, and providing support when needed are crucial. Developing methods to boost the motivation of cabin crew members falls under the responsibility of cabin chiefs. Acknowledging and supporting employees' performance during flights will help keep them motivated. When addressing negative situations, adopting a constructive approach is important. Cabin chiefs should act as a bridge between the company and employees, providing regular feedback to the company about employee performance.

How should the management of quiet quitting be handled from a company perspective?

Managers may not always have the opportunity to communicate regularly with each employee. Therefore, they may not be aware of how employees feel about their work and the problems they face in their work lives. This can lead to employees quiet quitting their jobs because they feel that their desires and needs are not being adequately addressed, and their expectations regarding their work are not being managed. Therefore, it would be beneficial for managers to regularly receive feedback from cabin crew members through cabin chiefs. An environment should be created where employees can share their ideas about their duties, positions, or any stage of a flight, and find creative solutions. To achieve this, frequent meetings should be planned. Taking employees' ideas into consideration will not only make them feel valued but also increase their commitment to their jobs.

Managers should clearly define career advancement paths for each employee. At this stage, it should not be forgotten that cabin crew members should be objectively evaluated when seeking promotion. For example, those who aspire to become cabin chiefs should have excellent language skills and communication abilities. Coordinating the team and responding to emergencies are significant responsibilities of a cabin supervisor. If an employee cannot meet the requirements for promotion, the company should communicate this constructively to the candidate. On the other hand, employees who want to improve themselves should be supported by the company and re-evaluated if they meet the criteria.

In airlines, planning flight schedules for cabin crew members as fairly and evenly as possible will prevent employees from working with low motivation. Especially for married employees with children, it would be appropriate not to schedule long layover duties. If possible, the requests of married employees who do not want layover duties should be taken into account.

Companies should pay employees what they deserve, and there should not be a significant disparity in salaries to keep employees focused on their jobs. If there are any adjustments to be made in salaries or other benefits, this should be communicated to employees in advance. In case of delayed salary payments or other payments, transparency should be maintained, and the authorities should make the necessary announcements to employees. Adherence to aviation rules and company procedures is undoubtedly essential among employees. However, even minor errors leading to punishment by the company can drive cabin crew members towards quiet quitting. It is recommended that companies be more careful when revoking an employee's title or seniority for punitive purposes in the future.

In conclusion, the growing trend of quiet quitting among cabin crew members will have negative consequences for both the airline company and the passenger experience. Taking necessary measures to increase employee motivation and commitment will help prevent quiet quitting and enhance the competitiveness of companies. In future research, it is recommended to increase the number of individuals interviewed to gain a deeper understanding of the issue. Additionally, investigating quiet quitting among cabin chiefs in the future could be considered."

REFERENCES

- Aktunç, İ. (2013). Kabin Memuru Tanımı, *Türk Hava Yolları Uçuş Eğitim Başkanlığı Cabin Interphone Dergisi*, 1, 9-10.
- Arar, T., Çetiner, N. & Yurdakul, G. (2023). Quiet Quitting: Building a Comprehensive Theoretical Framework, *Akademik Araştırmalar ve Çalışmalar Dergisi*, 15(28), 122-138.
- Curtisa, S.; Geslerb, W.; Smitha, G. & Washburnb, S. (2000). Approaches to Sampling and Case Selection in Qualitative Research: Examples in The Geography of Health, *Social Science & Medicine*, (50), 1002.
- Echterhoff, W., Poweleit, D., Schindler, U., & Kreuz, A. (1997) Innere Kündigung–Überwinden von Motivationsblockaden in Wirtschaft und Verwaltung, *Zeitschrift Führung + Organisation*, (1), 33–37.
- Gallup (2022). *Is Quiet Quitting Real?*, <https://www.gallup.com/workplace/398306/quiet-quitting-real.aspx>
- Granger, B. (2022). "Quiet quitting: the latest workplace trend to combat burnout". *Qualtrics*. <https://www.qualtrics.com/blog/quiet-quitting/>
- Gupte, A. (2022). *Decoding Quiet Quitting*, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/decoding-quiet-quitting-ashlesha-gupte>
- Hiltunen, H. (2023). *Quiet Quitting Phenomenon in Finnish Aviation Industry*. [Bachelor Thesis]. Haaga-Helia University of Applied Sciences Degree in Aviation Business.
- Hitchins, S. (2022). *Quiet Quitting is Dividing the Workforce. Here's How to Bring Everyone Back Together*. *Entrepreneur*. <https://www.entrepreneur.com/leadership/quiet-quitting-is-taking-over-the-workforce-heres-how-to/434560>
- Hymes, K. (2021). *The Great Resignation' Misses the Point*. www.wired.com/story/great-resignation-misses-the-point
- Kumar, T. S. (2022). How to Handle Notice Period in Organization & Emotional Balancing During Resignation & Finding New Job. Case Study on Quite Quit, Shodhshauryam, *International Scientific Refereed Research Journal*, 5(5), 9-12.
- Pearce, M. (2022). *Gen Z didn't coin 'quiet quitting' Gen X did*. <https://www.latimes.com/entertainment-arts/story/2022-08-27/la-ent-quiet-quitting-origins>
- Pandey, E. (2022). *The staying power of quiet quitting*. <https://www.axios.com/2022/09/21/quiet-quitting-gen-z-work-jobs-minimum>
- Ratnatunga, J. (2022). Quiet Quitting: The Silent Challenge of Performance Management, *Jamar*, 20(2), 13-20.

- Robinson, A. (2022). *Quiet Quitting: How to Prevent & Combat it at Work*. <https://teambuilding.com/blog/quiet-quitting>
- Scheibner, N. & Hapkemeyer, J. (2013). Innere Kündigung als Thema in der Organisationsentwicklung. Organisationsberatung, *Supervision, Coaching*, 20(4), 461-472.
- Schroth, H. (2019). Are You Ready for Gen Z in the Workplace?. *California Management Review*, 61(3), 5-18.
- Seçer, B. (2011). İş Güvencesizliğinin İçsel İşten Ayrılma ve Yaşam Doyumuna Etkisi, *ISGUC The Journal of Industrial Relations Human Resources*, 13(4), 43-60.
- SHGM (2023). *Havacılık Personeli*. <https://web.shgm.gov.tr/tr/havacilik-personeli/2138-kabin-memuru>
- Srivastava, S., & Kanpur, R. (2014). A Study on Quality of Work Life: Key Elements & It's Implications, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 16(3), 54-59.
- Tong, G. C. (2022). *Is 'Quiet Quitting' A Good Idea? Here's What Workplace Experts Say. Make It*. <https://www.cnbc.com/2022/08/30/is-quiet-quitting-a-good-idea-heres-what-workplace-experts-say.html>
- Tümüklü, A. (2000). Eğitim Bilimi Araştırmalarında Etkin Olarak Kullanılabilecek Nitel Bir Araştırma Tekniği: Görüşme, *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 24, 547.
- Xu, X. (2020). Examining an Asymmetric Effect Between Online Customer Reviews Emphasis and Overall Satisfaction Determinants, *Journal of Business Research*, 106, 196-210.
- Yıldız, D. (2023). Örgütlerde İşgören ve İşverenlerin Güncel Sorunu: Sessiz İstifa, *Social Sciences Research Journal*, 12(6), 795-802.
- Youthall (2022). *Sessiz İstifa*. <https://www.youthall.com/tr/company/ebooks/sessiz-istifa>